

Sample Name: PVC Vir Flu 1 µm

Material: Polyvinyl Chloride

Size: <1 µm

Supplier: SigmaAldrich Merck, no. 346764, powder, Aimplas, TNO

Density: 1,4 (g/cm³)*

Production Partner: TNO

Storage Conditions: Refrigerated and dark

*The density may vary due to the presence of Fluorescein

Summary

Physical Characteristics

- Median diameter (D50_v) = 3,54 µm
- Particles have an irregular morphology
- 1.1 x10¹³ particles per gram
- 14188 cm²/g surface area

Chemical Characteristics

- C=O peak (1722 cm⁻¹) due to oxidation observed in FTIR spectrum
- Fluorescent moiety is Fluorescein

Description of terms

- D[4,3]:Volume mean (µm)
- D[3,2]:Surface area mean (µm)
- D[2,1]: Spherical particle mean (µm)
- D[1,0]: Number length mean (µm)
- D50_v: Median diameter (volume basis, µm)
- D50_N: Median diameter (number basis, µm)
- N_w: Number of particles per gram plastic (#/g)
- A_w: Surface area of particles per gram plastic (cm²/g)

Particle Size Distribution (using *Static Light Scattering (SLS)* provided by TNO)

D[4,3]	D[3,2]	D[2,1]	D[1,0]	D50 _N	D50 _V	N _w	A _w
5,24	3,06	2,04	1,35	1,02	3,54	1.1 x10 ¹³	14188

